

Lepanthes martae-aleidae (Orchidaceae), a replacement name for a Cuban orchid

Lepanthes martae-aleidae (Orchidaceae), un nuevo nombre de reemplazo para una orquídea cubana

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Dr. Carl Luer (1991) described several new species of *Pleurothallidinae* (Orchidaceae) collected during an expedition to Colombia in 1987. One of them is *Lepanthes marthae* Luer & R. Escobar dedicated to Sra. Martha Posada de Robledo, who discovered the plant, jointly with Sra. Ligia Moreno de Posada, in the Department of Antioquia.

In 1999, Cuban botanist Marta Aleida Díaz collected an undescribed *Lepanthes* species in eastern Cuba and sent a duplicate in exchange to Luer. Luer (2001) described the new species as *Lepanthes martae* Luer. In the protologue, the collecting locality is not mentioned and therefore the holotype specimen (in HAC) couldn't be traced. Subsequently, Llamacho (2004) mentions that the species occurs in the Toa-Baracoa Mountain Massif.

According to the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi and plants (Turland & al. 2018), *Lepanthes martae* Luer is to be treated as a later homonym of *Lepanthes marthae* Luer & R. Escobar (Turland & al. 2018: Art. 53.2, Example 11), and is therefore an illegitimate name (Turland & al. 2018: Art. 53.1). I here present a replacement name for *Lepanthes martae* Luer, also dedicated to Dra. Marta Aleida Díaz Dumas, using her full given name.

Taxonomic treatment

Lepanthes martae-aleidae Mor. Mart., **nom. nov.** ≡ *Lepanthes martae* Luer, *Selbyana* 22: 109. 2001, **nom. illeg.** (non *Lepanthes marthae* Luer & R. Escobar, *Orquideología* 18(1): 60. 1991). Holotype: [specimen] Cuba, Collection data unavailable [according to the protologue], 1999, *M. A. Díaz 10* (HAC [n.v.]; isotype: MO [n.v.]).

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

A. Morales conceived the original idea, searched and reviewed the literature, the original draws and the protologues, also processed the information and wrote the manuscript.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

Conflict of interest: The author declares that she has no conflict of interest.

Consent for publication: The author has consented to publishing this work.

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